

Improved Oxidase Mimetic Activity by Doping Praseodymium in Ceria Nanocubes

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ABSTRACT

Ceria nanoparticles have demonstrated great potential as catalysts for oxidation reactions in a wide range of applications due to their outstanding redox properties. In this study, well-defined single crystal CeO₂ nanocubes are confirmed to present intrinsic oxidase-like activity allowing them to quickly oxidize organic dyes in acidic conditions. Praseodymium (10 mol.%) doped ceria nanocubes have been successfully synthesized by a hydrothermal method. The as-synthesized Pr-doped ceria nanocubes exhibit not only a higher reducibility but also an enhanced oxidase-like activity within a wide range of concentrations and durations. A variety of techniques were used to characterize the structure, composition and redox behavior of the nanocubes such as X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP), X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS), High Resolution Electron Microscopy (HREM), Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS), Temperature Programmed Reduction (TPR) or Oxygen Storage Capacity (OSC) measurements. The kinetics of their oxidase mimetic activity has been studied and a mechanism has been proposed on how the Pr incorporation could affect the energy level of the bands in ceria, and hence facilitate the oxidation reaction. Since the ceria nanocubes are not susceptible to denaturation or decomposition, they could potentially provide a highly stable replacement or alternative to traditional enzymes in biotechnical applications or in experiments such as enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceria and CeO₂-based compounds have attracted great interest due to their extensive applications in heterogeneous catalysis,^{1,2} solid oxide fuel cells³ or biomedicine.⁴ Because of its unique redox properties, it has been demonstrated that CeO₂ possesses excellent catalytic properties in different chemical reactions such as CO oxidation,⁵ total oxidation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons,⁶ NO reduction,⁷ soot combustion⁸ and H₂ oxidation.⁹ In the CO oxidation reaction process, CO abstracts an oxygen atom from a surface –Ce^{IV}-O- linkage, creating an oxygen vacancy and resulting in the oxidation of CO. The oxygen vacancy is refilled in the final step of the catalytic cycle after O₂ dissociation on the reduced surface. Therefore, the role of ceria is similar to that of an oxidase.^{14,15} An oxidase is an enzyme that catalyzes an oxidation-reduction reaction involving molecular oxygen (O₂).¹² Recently, several studies have been published on the oxidase mimetic activity of nanoceria.^{10,11} In particular, studies by Perez et al.¹⁰ have revealed that ceria nanoparticles are able to quickly oxidize several organic substrates without any additional oxidizing reagents. Attempts to enhance the oxidase mimetic activity have since then started, e.g. by coating particles with polymers to increase their dispersion and to control their efficiency. Later Gao et al.¹³ have argued that instead of being postulated as an oxidase mimic, ceria nanoparticles behaved as an oxidant which dissolved completely after being reduced under acidic conditions.

The main reason for the oxidase-like activity of ceria above mentioned can be attributed to its high Oxygen Storage Capacity (OSC), being considered as an efficient

“oxygen buffer” because it is able to release and store oxygen when treated alternatively under reducing and oxidizing atmospheres, by means of a facile $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ redox cycle. Besides, numerous evidences indicate that various structures and morphologies of ceria present some unique properties different from those of traditional ceria particles. For example, nanoceria with well-defined shapes has an apparent advantage in enhancing the catalytic activity because it exposes more active facets which might facilitate the redox cycles.¹⁶ Meanwhile doping ceria with other elements, such as transition metals (Zr)¹⁷ or other lanthanides (La, Pr and Yb),¹⁸⁻²² has been proven to enhance the redox properties of ceria due to an increase in the concentration of oxygen vacancies and oxygen mobility in the oxide. It has been observed that mixing ceria with suitable aliovalent cationic metal dopants enhances the redox behavior of CeO_2 . In particular, Pr can greatly improve OSC of ceria due to its $\text{Pr}^{4+}/\text{Pr}^{3+}$ redox couple. Pr-doped ceria solid solutions have attracted much attention due to their applications as nontoxic red ceramic pigments, and also because they have been considered promising ion-conducting electrolytes and oxygen storage materials.²³⁻²⁵ Likewise, it has been verified that Pr-doped mesoporous ceria solid solutions are efficient photocatalysts for degradation of Rhodamine B. Such activity, related to a radical oxidation process, was clearly improved after incorporation of Pr into a 2-D mesoporous ceria.¹⁸

It was also found that ceria nanoshapes with defined surface planes as $\{110\}$ and $\{111\}$ -facet dominant (nanorods), $\{100\}$ -facet dominant (nanocubes) and $\{111\}$ -facet dominant (nano-octahedra), exhibit different catalytic responses in the CO

oxidation reaction, following the activity order nanorods > nanocubes > octahedra.⁵ Both experimental^{26,27} and theoretical^{28,29} studies have shown that oxygen vacancies are easier to form on {110} and {100} than on {111} facets. Considering all these findings, in this study we synthesized well-defined ceria and Pr-doped ceria nanocubes using a hydrothermal method. The as-synthesized CeO₂ NC and Pr-doped CeO₂ NC, both with high exposure of {100} facets (ratio ≥ 84%), were functionally characterized in terms of their oxidase-like activities for the first time. Their structure as well as redox behavior were also investigated in order to understand the mechanism of the nanoceria induced oxidation.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Synthesis

A hydrothermal method described in previous papers^{30,31} was used. 125 mL of 11.5 M NaOH (Alfa Aesar, 98%) and 115 mL of 0.1 M Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O (Alfa Aesar, 99.5%) were mixed and stirred in a 300 mL Teflon container for 30 min in order to synthesize CeO₂ nanocubes (NC). The Teflon container was then sealed with a Teflon lid and placed into a stainless steel autoclave. The reaction mixture was kept at 180 °C for 24 h in an oven. Afterwards, the mixture was cooled down to room temperature, it was centrifuged and washed with deionized water several times and then with ethanol once (Panreac, Absolute Ethanol). Finally, the samples were dried at 80 °C for 24 h in an oven. A yellowish powder was obtained as shown in Figure SI.1(a).

The synthesis of the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample was carried out following the same procedure. However, the concentrations of Ce and Pr precursors were adjusted to

0.094 M $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.01 M $\text{Pr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sigma Aldrich, 99.99%). At the end a reddish powder was obtained (Figure SI.1(b)).

2.2. Physical and Compositional Characterization

X-Ray diffraction patterns were recorded on a D8 ADVANCE diffractometer of Bruker using the $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation, with a range of 5-110°, a step of 0.02° and a step time of 1s. The software DiffracPlus was used to measure the width of the {111} diffraction peak in order to calculate the particle size using the Scherrer equation. ICP measurements were carried out in an ICP-AES Iris Intrepid equipment of Thermal Elemental to determine the actual Pr content of the doped nanocubes. Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface areas of the samples were determined in a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 via nitrogen adsorption at -196 °C. Prior to the analysis, the samples were degasified at 150 °C for 2 h under vacuum.

The surface chemical composition in Ce and Pr of the samples was characterized by XPS. The analyses were performed on a Kratos Axis Ultra DLD instrument. Spectra were recorded using monochromatized $\text{Al K}\alpha$ radiation (1486.6 eV), with an X-ray power of 150 W. The spectrometer was operated in the constant analyzer energy mode, with pass energy of 20 eV. Powder samples were pressed into pellets, which were stuck on a double-sided adhesive conducting polymer tape and analyzed without any further treatment. 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample was also submitted to a thermal treatment with a 5%O₂/He flow at 370 °C for 1 h in a catalytic chamber attached to the spectrometer, so it could be analyzed without being exposed to the air. Surface charging effects were compensated by making use of the Kratos coaxial

neutralization system. The binding energy scale was calibrated with respect to the C 1s signal at 284.8 eV.

The samples were also investigated using a variety of transmission and scanning transmission electron microscopy techniques. These analyses were all performed in a JEOL 2010-F scanning transmission electron microscope with 0.19 nm spatial resolution at Scherzer defocus conditions in HREM. Scanning transmission electron microscopy-high angle annular dark field (STEM-HAADF) images were obtained by using an electron probe of 0.5 nm of diameter at a camera length of 8 cm. EELS analyses were carried out by using an ENFINA spectrometer (Gatan), using a convergence angle of 1.82 mrad, a collection angle of 0.64 mrad, an exposure time of 2 seconds with a dispersion of 0.3 eV/channel and an aperture of 3 mm. In order to increase the signal-to-noise ratio of the as-collected EELS spectra, PCA algorithm was employed using hyperspy software.³²

2.3. Redox Properties

Temperature programmed reduction with H₂ (H₂-TPR) started with a pretreatment consisting in an oxidation under a 5% O₂/He flow (60 mL/min) at 500 °C for 1 h. After the oxidation pretreatment, the samples were cooled in the same 5% O₂/He flow down to 150 °C, and then, the flow was switched to pure He down to room temperature. The samples were reduced in a 60 mL/min flow of 5% H₂/Ar with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and a maximum reduction temperature of 950 °C, keeping the sample at this final temperature for 1 h. The outlet of H₂-TPR equipment was connected

to a ThermoStar GSD301T1 mass spectrometer of Pfeiffer Vacuum. The mass/charge ratio (m/z) values used to monitor H_2 consumption were 2 and 18 for the concomitant formation of H_2O .

OSC measurements were carried out by a thermogravimetric method, using a SDT Q600 horizontal thermobalance. The pretreatment used in these experiments was an oxidation in a 5% O_2/He flow at 500 °C for 1 h. Then the sample was cooled down in the same flow to 150 °C, and kept at this temperature for 30 min. The process of analysis included measuring the weight loss of the sample in a 5% H_2/Ar flow, with a flowrate of 60 mL/min, at isothermal regime at selected increasing temperatures (200, 350, 500 and 700 °C). To proceed from one temperature to the following, a heating rate of 10 °C/min was used upon reaching the desired temperature, which was held for 1 h.

2.4. Oxidase Activity

The oxidase mimetic activity of the samples was studied by investigating their capability to catalyze the oxidation of 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB). A 1 mM TMB solution was prepared by diluting 100 mM TMB stock solution (in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)) with 10 mM pH 4.0 of acetate buffer. The solution was then stirred thoroughly to avoid precipitation. The ceria nanocube solution was prepared dispersing CeO_2 NCs or 10%Pr- CeO_2 NCs in Milli Q water after washing and centrifuging the nanocubes at 12000 rpm for 10 min three times. The nanoceria solution was sonicated for 2 h before each measurement. The UV-VIS absorption spectra of TMB before and after the addition of nanocubes were obtained through a SHIMADZU UV-2450

spectrophotometer. Steady kinetic assays were monitored in a time course mode at 652 nm using SpectraMax M2e microplate reader (Molecular Devices, US). To explore and compare kinetic activities, the concentrations of the nanocubes were varied (60 μ M, 600 μ M and 6 mM) with 200 μ L TMB of fixed concentration and vice versa. Similarly, the concentration of nanocubes were kept at 6 mM, and 200 μ L TMB at 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5 mM were applied to calculate the steady kinetics analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Morphology of Ceria Nanocubes

Figure 1 shows representative HREM and STEM-HAADF images of the CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC samples. These images confirm that both samples are comprised of cubic-shaped nanocrystals. Figures 1(c) and 1(d) depict the analyses of the spatial frequencies observed in the HREM images (Digital Diffraction Pattern, DDP, included as insets), showing the presence of {002} reflections of fluorite-type ceria when looked down a [001] zone axis. On the other hand, {002} and {111} reflections were observed when these nanocubes oriented along a [011] direction (Figures 1(e) and 1(f)).

The particle size distributions of the as-synthesized CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC, obtained by (S)TEM studies, are presented in Figure 2. The edge lengths of roughly 150 nanocubes were measured for each sample. The edge length distributions of the two samples are very similar, both in the range 5 to 50 nm. Therefore the average cube sizes were very close for CeO₂ NC (26 nm) and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC (27 nm).

However it seems that the latter has a higher percentage of smaller cubes. Thus, in CeO₂ NC only 8% of the cubes falls between 5 and 10 nm while 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC has 23% within this range.

The specific surface areas of the two samples were estimated using the edge length distributions, by assuming in first approach a model of nontruncated perfect cubes. The estimated values were 33 m²/g for CeO₂ NC and 23 m²/g for 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC as listed in Table 1. These values are very close to the specific BET surface areas obtained experimentally by N₂ physisorption measurements (38 and 25 m²/g), which indicates that the size distributions established by STEM are representative of the samples at macroscopic level.

The contribution of different crystallographic planes to the total exposed surface can be calculated by using the data from HREM. For CeO₂ NC, the percentage of {100}, {110}, and {111} facets are 84%, 16% and < 1%, as previously reported.^{30,31} For 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC, the corresponding percentages are 89%, 11% and 0% for the same facets. In a word, the surface crystallography of the two samples is very similar.

3.2. Structure and Composition of Ceria Nanocubes

XRD diagrams of the CeO₂ NCs and Pr-doped CeO₂ NCs are shown in Figure 3. All the diffraction peaks observed in both CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC samples can be attributed to a fluorite-like, face-centered cubic structure (Fm3m) ceria, in good agreement with TEM results. The sharp diffraction peaks clearly indicate a single crystal state of both types of NCs. The XRD profiles for CeO₂ NCs and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NCs are almost identical (no apparent angle shifts or signal asymmetries were observed

on the XRD diagrams (Figure 3(b)), which might be caused by the similarity between the cationic radius of Pr^{4+} (96 pm) and Ce^{4+} (97 pm). The lattice parameters and average particle size of both nanocubes can be estimated from the Scherrer equation as seen in Table 1, being 21 and 29 nm for CeO_2 NCs and 10%Pr- CeO_2 NCs respectively. Additionally, the lattice parameters of these two samples were calculated and included in Table 1, being the same (0.54 nm) since there is no significant shift of the diffraction peaks after the incorporation of Pr, in contrast to that observed in our previous work dealing with La-doped ceria nanocubes.³¹

The chemical composition of 10%Pr- CeO_2 NCs was determined by ICP as shown in Table 1. The molar concentration of Pr is 9.7%, which is very similar to the expected value 10%. Figure 4 shows the XP spectra for Pr 3d and Ce 3d core levels, which a depth around 3.5 nm from the surface can be analyzed.³³ It can be seen in Table 1 that the Pr composition on the surface of the sample, 9.4 mol% Pr, is also very similar to ICP results, which represent the average bulk composition of the sample. These results clearly indicate that Pr distributes homogeneously in the 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC sample.

XPS analyses in Figure 4 also allow us studying the oxidation state of Pr and Ce. Figure 4(a) show the Pr 3d core level for the 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC sample, as-synthesized and after being *in situ* oxidized at 370 °C. The characteristic Pr^{4+} signal at 968 eV^{34,35} cannot be observed in any of the two spectra, indicating that all the praseodymium that can be analyzed by XPS (i.e. that within the first 3.5 nm from the surface) is 100% Pr^{3+} , even after being submitted to an oxidizing treatment in the catalytic chamber attached

to the spectrometer. No other kind of Pr containing species, different from Pr^{3+} incorporated in a mixed Pr-Ce oxide solid solution, was detected by XPS. The collection of Pr 3d spectra, Figure SI.2, can be seen the Pr^{4+} signal corresponding to pure praseodymia. In this case, the preferred oxidation state of praseodymium species close to the surface is +3 for the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NCs. This result is in good agreement with previous data in the literature.^{24,25,36,37} Concerning the major lanthanide, cerium, the XPS results (Figure 4(b)) indicate that this element is mainly present as Ce^{4+} on the surface of both pure and Pr-doped CeO₂ NCs. Thus, the fraction of Ce^{3+} on the outermost surface layers of CeO₂ NC amounts only to 2% but it is below the detection limitation on the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample.

Spectrum-line EELS analyses of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample can provide further information about the composition of this sample. Thus, EELS spectra of the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NCs were recorded point by point, every 0.5 nm, along a line on a nanocube starting at one surface, crossing through the bulk of the nanocube and exiting at the opposite surface, as marked on the STEM-HAADF image shown in Figure 5(a). As revealed by the HAADF-STEM image intensity profile along the path, Figure 5(b), the thickness of the cube remains fairly constant along most of the line scan. Note also that the Pr M_{4,5} signals can be clearly detected in Spectrum I of Figure 5(c), which corresponds to an average of 66 individual spectra recorded on the bulk positions of the cube (marked on Figure 5(a)). Spectrum II, corresponding to the average of all the spectra contained in a surface layer whose thickness is the same as that analyzed by XPS (3.5 nm), tiny Pr-M_{4,5} signals still can be observed. Finally,

Spectrum III in Figure 5(c) corresponds to the average of the first 4 spectra from a surface layer just 1 nm of thickness. In this latter spectrum the Pr peaks are not as clearly distinguishable from the noise as in the other spectra. Nevertheless, if we consider that the total intensity of the Ce peaks is in this case very low, due to the fact that we are analyzing the thinnest part of the crystallite, and that the intensity ratio between Pr/Ce $M_{4,5}$ peaks is roughly 16%, it is clear that in this spectrum the intensity of the Pr signals should be in the order of that observed experimentally. Since these data suggest that the ratio between the Ce- $M_{4,5}$ and Pr- $M_{4,5}$ signals retains roughly constant along the path, it can be concluded that EELS experiments also certifies a homogeneous distribution of Pr throughout the nanocube volume. The Pr concentration determined by nanoanalysis in this case is 12 ± 3 at.%. Similar results were obtained when the measurements were repeated on different nanocubes of the Pr-doped NC sample. Combining the results obtained by ICP, XPS and STEM-EELS, it can be concluded that the composition of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC is uniform and that Pr mixed with Ce at atomic level. Somacescu et al. stated that uniform Ce_{1-x}Pr_xO_{2-δ} solid solutions could be synthesized by hydrothermal methods with surfactants in a wide range of x (x = 0, 0.1, 0.5 and 0.9).³⁹ Our synthesis with 10 mol% of Pr maintains in particular a nanocube type morphology for the solid solution product.

EELS can be used to probe the oxidation state of cerium. The fine structure details of the EELS spectra of Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ differ in terms of the exact energy position of the M₄ and M₅ white lines as well as in their relative intensity, Figure SI.3.³⁸ Moreover, both the M₄ and M₅ peaks present a low intensity shoulder at their

high-energy side in the EELS spectrum of Ce^{4+} , which are not observed in the case of Ce^{3+} . Concerning these changes in the fine structure of the Ce $M_{4,5}$ edge of Cerium, Sharma et al.⁴⁰ have proposed the use of the ratio of the intensities of the M_5/M_4 peaks at their maxima to detect the presence of both oxidation states. The value of this ratio for a sample containing only Ce^{4+} amounts to 1.18, whereas it decreases down to 0.87 in Ce^{3+} pure samples. Intermediate values would indicate the presence of mixed $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ situations. The closer the value of this ratio to the upper value, the larger the fraction of Ce^{4+} , though a fully quantitative and direct relationship cannot be simply established.

Figure SI.3 plots the evolution of the M_5/M_4 cerium lines intensity ratio in the two investigated samples, as a function of the distance from the surface of the cubes. Note that in both cases, the values tend to increase from the surface positions to the bulk of the crystallites. This indicates that in both samples reduced ceria species locate on the surface. The value of the ratio observed in bulk locations does not reach the value expected for a totally oxidized Ce^{4+} state, which is consistent with the presence of a thin Ce^{3+} -containing surface layer covering the whole crystallites. It also should be highlighted that in general, the ratio observed on the 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC sample lies, within the first 4 nm layer (which is roughly the maximum depth analyzed by XPS), above that of CeO_2 NC, which points out to a lower concentration of reduced ceria in the former. An apparent discrepancy between this result and the acquired EELS data can be perceived, as the latter indicated the existence of a high proportion of Ce^{3+} on the surface of both catalysts. Nevertheless, that disparity could be explained taking into

account the reduction effect of the electron beam in transmission electron microscopy.³⁸

In particular, the concentration of Ce^{3+} in the very first surface layer (<0.5 nm) is much lower in the praseodymium containing oxide. Finally, this plot also indicates that the thickness of the Ce^{3+} -containing layer is larger in CeO_2 -NC. In this respect, in this sample the M_4/M_5 intensity ratio reaches a plateau at roughly 9 nm from the surface whereas this is observed just at 4-5 nm in 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC. All these observations evidence a much more oxidized state of cerium at surface level in the oxide cubes containing praseodymium.

Summarizing the EELS and XPS results in relation to the oxidation state of the lanthanides, it is clear that in the 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC sample all the Pr present on the surface layers is fully reduced, as Pr^{3+} , which gives at least a total 10% reduction on the surface. According to EELS, reduced Ce^{3+} species are also present in both CeO_2 NC and 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC samples, but XPS indicate a larger contribution of reduced Ce^{3+} in the former. In total, the surface of the CeO_2 NC contains around 2% Ce^{3+} species, whereas 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC sample contains 10% Pr^{3+} and an amount of Ce^{3+} much lower than 2%. This means that from the Ce sites at the surface, the fraction of them available as Ce^{4+} is larger in the 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC sample. On the other hand, in this same oxide only Pr^{3+} (10% of all available lanthanides) species are available at the surface. Concerning oxygen vacancies, the total reduction state of the surface is roughly 2% in the CeO_2 NC cubes and only slightly larger than 10% in 10%Pr- CeO_2 NC. This indicates that there will be at least 5 times more oxygen vacancies in the latter.

Therefore, there are both qualitative and quantitative differences in the surface composition between the two types of as-prepared oxide nanocubes.

3.3. Redox Properties and Oxidase Activity

The redox behavior and oxidase mimetic of ceria nanocubes are examined by H₂-TPR, OSC, and TMB oxidation experiments.

3.3.1 H₂-TPR Characterization

Figure 6 displays the H₂O evolution and H₂ consumption signals during H₂-TPR of the ceria nanocubes. Comparing Figure 6(a) and 6(b), a good agreement between the production of water and the consumption of hydrogen is clearly seen, which indicates that all the water evolution observed in Figure 6(a) correspond to abstraction of lattice oxygen from the nanocubes. The reduction of the CeO₂ NC reference sample shows a first broad maximum about 527 °C in the m/z: 18 signal, followed by another rather wide high intensity signal peaking at 830 °C. These two peaks can be attributed to surface and bulk reduction of the ceria nanocubes, respectively.⁹ When Pr is incorporated into the nanocubes, the reducibility is clearly enhanced, especially at low temperatures, as the reduction peaks shift to lower temperatures, namely 463, 517 and 768 °C and the intensity of the low temperature signals grows to become larger than the high temperature peak. Similar results have been reported for nanocrystalline Pr-doped ceria by Reddy et al.⁴¹ It seems clear that 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC requires less energy to be reduced, hence it possesses a higher reducibility than the CeO₂ NC sample.

3.3.2 OSC results

OSC results of both types of ceria nanocubes are shown in Figure 7. The

10%Pr-CeO₂ NC presents larger oxygen weight losses than the pure CeO₂ NC above 350 °C. This result agrees well with the higher reducibility of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC observed in the H₂-TPR experiments just mentioned. The weight loss difference between the two samples increases with reduction temperature.

In the H₂-TPR analyses (Figure 6(a)), the first reduction peak of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC at 463 °C might be attributed to the reduction of Pr⁴⁺ to Pr³⁺.⁴² However, it is difficult to separate the reduction of Ce from that of Pr solely based on the OSC results. Actually, OSC measurements represent the total value of oxygen evolved from the reduction of both ceria and praseodymia. In any case, the OSC results suggest that, at the same temperature, more lattice oxygen can be taken out from 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC than from CeO₂ NC, and thus, ceria reduction becomes easier in the Pr-doped nanocubes.

A quantitative analysis of the total evolved oxygen can be performed. There is 10 mol% Pr content in the Pr-doped ceria nanocubes, the maximum amount of oxygen that can be related to transformation of Pr⁴⁺ into Pr³⁺, in case it was fully oxidized after the pretreatment in oxygen at 250 °C, would be 50 mmol. However, XPS results indicate that within the first 3.5 nm surface layer, praseodymium is present only as Pr³⁺. Using the nanocube size distribution, it is possible to make an estimation of the fraction of praseodymium atoms comprised within this surface layer. The obtained amount is 44%. Accordingly, in case all the remaining (56%) Pr in the bulk of the cubes would be present as Pr⁴⁺, their transformation to Pr³⁺ during reduction would involve a maximum amount of 28 mmol of oxygen.

After reduction at 500 °C the total evolved oxygen (73 mmol) is much larger

than the addition of these 28 mmol to the oxygen evolved in the pure CeO₂ NC sample (27 mmol). This is also the case at 700 °C (153 mmol of total evolved oxygen in the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC vs 28+83 mmol from CeO₂ NC), which clearly evidences a large improvement in the reducibility of Ce⁴⁺ at these temperatures when both lanthanides are homogeneously mixed within the nanocubes.

After reduction at low temperature of 350 °C, the evolved oxygen is higher in the Pr-modified cubes than in the pure ceria cubes, but the total (13 mmol) is below the oxygen which can be attributed to total transformation of Pr. Therefore, we cannot distinguish the observed reduction effects between the two lanthanides. Previous in-situ TEM-EELS studies have evidenced that at these temperatures Pr is the first element which can be reduced in conventional, irregularly shaped, mixed Ce-Pr oxides.⁴² Therefore we should expect that oxygen evolved after reduction at 350 °C could be mostly related to reduction of Pr in the modified nanocubes.

3.3.3 Oxidase Activity

The oxidase activity of the nanocubes was investigated with TMB under acidic conditions. It has been reported that the colorless TMB can be oxidized to blue color in aqueous solution.^{43,44} The oxidation process of TMB has been well studied and confirmed by optical and EPR spectroscopy.^{43,44} As depicted schematically in Figure 8(a), at the beginning of the oxidation, a cation free radical establishes a rapid equilibrium with a charge-transfer TMB complex of the parent diamine and product diimine. These charge-transfer complex species present absorbance peaks at 370 and 652 nm, which are responsible for the blue color observed during the oxidation of

TMB. The blue product consists of the TMB cation free radical in equilibrium with the charge-transfer complex (TMB-TMB⁺). When sulfuric acid is added, further oxidation occurs to produce the two-electron oxidation product, a diimine derivative of TMB. This TMB diimine absorbs at 450 nm and the solution appears yellow, as shown in Figure 8(b).

Because the oxidation reaction is specifically represented by the absorbance at 652 nm, TMB dye can be used quantitatively to indicate the oxidation process and kinetics. Therefore TMB has been used as oxidation substrate and often requires hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) to serve as an electron receptor or oxidizing agent to detect certain proteins in the common biochemical enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.¹⁰ Perez et al. found that dextran-coated ceria nanoparticles could oxidize TMB quickly without H₂O₂, which is the first report on the oxidase-like activity of nanoceria. It was found that the catalytic efficiency of nanoceria is dependent on pH, size and polymer thickness. Lower pH, smaller size and thinner coating on the nanoparticle can all lead to higher activity.¹⁰ Liu et al.¹¹ continued to study the oxidase performance of nanoceria with adsorbed DNA polymers. Hayat et al.⁴⁵ reported the oxidase mimetic property of nanoceria and its potential colorimetric assays for detection of dopamine and catechol. Their results have demonstrated that the commercially available ceria nanoparticles possess such oxidase activity, which may replace tyrosinase (a commonly used oxidative enzyme for the detection of phenolic compounds).

On such basis, in this study we explore the oxidase functions of our as-synthesized CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC. Figure 8(b) shows the UV-visible light

absorption spectrum of TMB before and after mixing with 600 μM of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC. The spectra were measured after more than 2 h when the color change stabilized. The appearance of absorption peaks at 370 and 652 nm indicate the occurrence of oxidized TMB. When 2M sulfuric acid was further added to the mixture, the solution quickly turns yellow, with the absorbance peak shifting to 450 nm. Similar spectra were obtained for the CeO₂ NCs. This suggests that our synthesized nanocubes demonstrate an oxidase-like activity similar to that previously reported for ceria nanoparticles.

Furthermore, the kinetics of TMB oxidation was investigated. Figure 9(a) shows the absorbance change at 652 nm of TMB with different concentrations of ceria nanocubes. The amount of oxidized TMB, which is linearly related to absorbance, increases with the nanoceria concentration. Under the same conditions, the performance of CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC are rather different, particularly at higher concentrations. For example, when the concentration of CeO₂ NC (or Pr-doped CeO₂ NC) is 6 mM, the steady-state absorbance catalyzed by 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC is 0.76 while it is only 0.24 for CeO₂ NC. It means that more than a threefold quantity of TMB has been oxidized by 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC than by pure CeO₂ NC. Such difference is even larger if the surface area of the two materials is taken into account. Since the process involves necessarily adsorption of the substrate to be oxidized on the surface of the nanocubes, specific surface area must be an important factor. If this is considered, the difference between the specific activities per unit surface area increases up to roughly a 5 times factor.

Figure 9 (b) to (d) present the dynamic change of absorbance per unit surface

area for CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC at 60 μM, 600 μM and 6 mM concentration. First, the absorption and color change are fast in all cases, taking place mostly within minutes, suggesting that the nanocubes catalyzed oxidation is a fast reaction. Secondly, the steady absorbance per unit surface area in the lower concentration of nanoceria suspension is higher than that at higher concentration. This might be because at lower nanoceria concentration the ratio of substrate/enzyme, i.e. TMB/nanocubes, is higher so that the final absorbance change per unit area of nanoceria is higher. Thirdly, at all concentrations, the initial reaction rate of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC, depicted as the slope of the dotted fit lines, is always higher than CeO₂ NC. This also suggests that the efficiency of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC as TMB oxidase is higher than that of the undoped CeO₂ NC.

3.3.4 Kinetics of TMB Oxidation

Often the activity of biochemical enzymes such as oxidases is quantitatively represented by the kinetics parameter K_m . This parameter is obtained from the Michaelis-Menten kinetics equation (Equation (1)) with data of enzyme working on various concentrations of substrates. By definition, the Michaelis constant K_m is the substrate concentration at which the reaction rate is half maximum. A smaller K_m indicates a higher enzyme activity, which means that reaction rate approaches the maximum rate more quickly. In this study we carried out similar kinetics experiment using nanoceria as oxidase in order to obtain and compare K_m values of the two samples.

The concentration of the TMB-derived oxidation product can be calculated from the absorbance data through Beer-Lambert Law using a molar absorption

coefficient of $39000 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$.⁴⁶ For example, the absorbance is 0.753 for 6 mM of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample. The concentration of oxidized TMB is calculated to be 0.02 mM. The steady state reaction rate with different TMB substrate concentrations can be obtained by calculating the slopes of initial absorbance change with time. The data is fitted with Michaelis-Menten kinetics equation (Equation (1)) and lineweaver-Burk plot (Equation (2)) to obtain the enzymatic parameter K_m .

$$v = \frac{V_m[s]}{K_m + [s]} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{v} = \frac{K_m}{V_m} \frac{1}{[s]} + \frac{1}{V_m} \quad (2)$$

Here v is reaction rate (mM/s), V_m is the maximum reaction rate, and $[s]$ is the concentration of substrate TMB (mM).

Figure 10(a) shows that the reaction rate (v in mM/s) varies with TMB concentration (1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5 and 3.0 mM) for the oxidation reaction catalyzed by 6 mM 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC and the fitting using Equations (1) and (2) respectively. The reaction rate of CeO₂ NC sample also has been calculated and displayed in Figure 10(b). Through calculations of initial changes of absorbance with time, apparent steady-state at different TMB concentrations are obtained. Thus, the K_m value for 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC is 0.27 mM. Similar measurements were performed on CeO₂ NC and its K_m is ~ 2.01 mM. The more than sevenfold difference of K_m between 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC and the undoped CeO₂ NC suggests that the oxidase activity of nanoceria can be significantly enhanced by doping Pr into ceria nanocubes.

3.4 Mechanism

The results above have demonstrated that both CeO₂ and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NCs can behave as oxidase-like materials. The oxidase enzyme is often related with a redox reaction involving molecular oxygen as the electron acceptor. In this study, the results show that the ceria nanocubes can quickly oxidize TMB substrate without additional oxidizing agents. Previously two mechanisms have been reported on the role of nanoceria in TMB oxidation. Perez et al.¹⁰ proposed that nanoceria functioned similar to oxidase while Gao et al.¹³ argued that nanoceria was simply an oxidizing agent because dissolution of nanoceria was observed. In our study it cannot be attributed to the latter mechanism because ceria nanocubes did not dissolve in the mixture of TMB and nanoceria. It is likely that our ceria nanocubes perform similar to an alternative mechanism recently proposed by Ni et al.⁴⁷. They found that both superoxide anion radicals ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$) and hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) appeared in the nanoceria solution without additional hydrogen peroxide. Therefore, it is possible that during the oxidation, O₂ (including gas phase and dissolved oxygen) is adsorbed on nanoceria and is reduced by nanoceria to produce $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ and $\bullet\text{OH}$ with intermediate H₂O₂. Both $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ and $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals are strong oxidizing agent and can oxidize TMB. At the same time, nanoceria is regenerated in the acidic solution. In this way nanoceria works similar to the oxidase enzyme.

Four aspects may contribute to the higher activity and higher reaction rate the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample than CeO₂ NC as an oxidase. First, it has been reported that the amount of Ce³⁺ on the surface is important for the oxidase activity of nanoceria. In

our case, according to XPS results, the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample does not possess Ce³⁺ on the surface, while there is only 2% Ce³⁺ for CeO₂ NC sample. However, the oxidation state of Pr on the surface of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample is Pr³⁺, no Pr⁴⁺ was observed. Taking account that Pr homogeneously distributes in 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample, 10% lanthanide exists in the form of +3. Similar to Ce, Pr³⁺ also can be oxidized to Pr⁴⁺ easily. Therefore, the total number of available Ce³⁺ or Pr³⁺ could be the main factor that accounts for the enhanced oxidase activity of Pr-doped CeO₂ NC. Secondly, nanoceria crystallites of smaller size (5 nm) are supposed to show higher activity than larger ones.¹⁰ In this study, our as-synthesized CeO₂ NC has 8% particles between 5 and 10 nm while the percentage is 23% for the Pr-doped nanocubes as in Figure 2. Nevertheless, the average nanocube size is quite similar for both types of samples and the BET surface area of CeO₂ NC is higher than that of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC (Table 1), i.e. the former exposes more surface for the oxidation reaction. Therefore, it seems that the impact of size or surface area is not a key issue for enhancing the oxidase activity of Pr-doped nanocubes. Thirdly, the ratio of active facets may play a role in tuning nanoceria's activity. It was reported that both {100} and {110} are more active than {111} facets.⁵ Our synthesized CeO₂ NC sample exposes 84% {100} and 16% {110} while 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC exposes 89% {100} and 11% {110}. Therefore, it is presumed that the active sites on facets are similar for CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC.

Finally, the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample exhibits better redox properties than CeO₂ NC, which might be is a decisive factor for the regeneration of Ce³⁺ species during the TMB oxidation process. Figure 11(a) show the valence band XPS data for a 100%

reduced praseodymium oxide, a strongly reduced cerium oxide, and the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample. These data show experimentally how the Pr 4f band lies between the O 2p and the Ce 4f bands. In the case of the Pr-doped CeO₂ NC, a new 4f band appears between the 4f bands for the pure oxides, suggesting that the electron transfer path can be possible not only from Ce 4f but also from Pr 4f to O 2p.

As shown in Figure 8(a), the oxidation of TMB is indeed an electron and charge transfer process. Therefore, the reaction rate is closely related to the ability of oxidase to transfer the electrons. Figure 11(b) presents the possible electron and charge transfer process for Pr-doped ceria nanocubes. When ceria nanocubes are mixed together with TMB, one electron can be easily transferred from TMB to the conduction band of CeO₂ (path 1) or to the Pr band of Pr-doped ceria (path 2), probably through several oxidizing agents such as as •O₂⁻ and •OH, resulting in the oxidation of TMB to blue TMB-TMB⁺⁺. Therefore, the easier the electron transfer, the faster TMB oxidation takes place.

Based on Eqs. (3) and (4), the energy positions of conduction band (CB) and valence band (VB) of CeO₂ can be calculated⁴⁸ from the band gap energy of CeO₂ E_g (3.5~3.60 eV)^{49,50}:

$$E_{CB} = \chi - E^C - 0.5E_g \quad (3)$$

$$E_g = E_{VB} - E_{CB} \quad (4)$$

Here $\chi = 5.56$ eV is the absolute electronegativity of CeO₂, $E^C = 4.5$ eV is the scaling factor relating the normal hydrogen electrode scale (NHE) to absolute vacuum scale.⁵¹

Using $E_g = 3.5$ eV, the energy of E_{CB} and E_{VB} can be calculated to be -0.69 eV and

2.81 eV, respectively.

It was proposed that the observed electron transition takes place between O 2p valence and Ce 4f conduction bands. As in Figure 11(a), the incorporation of Pr can result in the introduction of a Pr 4f band, which sits below the conduction band of Ce 4f, hence, reducing the band gap. The addition of the Pr 4f band within the optical band of ceria induces a broad absorption in the visible spectrum. This is why 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC appears in a reddish color. The excitation of electrons from Ce 4f into Pr 4f band leads to optical absorption in the visible spectrum and transforms undoped CeO₂ NC from a pale yellow solid to Pr-doped NC in red.⁵² Based on the optical absorbance spectra, Tuller et al. have measured the Pr band to be 1.6 eV⁵³ below the conductive band; therefore, we can deduce that the energy level of empty Pr band is ~0.91 eV vs NHE.

Because the energy level of Pr 4f band is lower than Ce 4f conduction band, the electron transfer is much easier for 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC, hence during the TMB oxidation, the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC performs better than the CeO₂ NC. Because Pr³⁺ is the dominant Pr component (at least on the surface), according to XPS results, the Pr band is likely to be filled. Therefore, the electron may possibly be passed on from Pr band to the oxygen vacancy V_O•• levels. Without the Pr band, the electron transfer has to be through the Ce 4f conduction band, which requires higher energy and consequently the oxidation is more difficult than in the Pr-doped ceria.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Pr-doped ceria nanocubes with homogeneous composition have been synthesized successfully by a hydrothermal method. Pr-doped CeO₂ NC presents

higher oxidase property and faster reaction rate than undoped CeO₂ NC. The higher percentage of lanthanide in oxidation state of +3 on the surface of Pr-doped CeO₂ NC could lead to its higher oxidase property. This potential application as oxidase might open a new door for Pr-doped nanostructured ceria in bioapplications.

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[§]The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have approval to the final version of the manuscript. L.J. and S.F.-G. contributed equally to this work.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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ABBREVIATIONS

XRD, X-ray diffraction; ICP, inductively coupled plasma; XPS, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy; HREM, high resolution electron microscopy; EELS, electron energy loss spectroscopy; TPR, temperature programmed reduction; OSC, oxygen storage capacity; TMB, 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine; DMSO, dimethyl sulfoxide; CB, conduction band; VB, valence band; NHE, normal hydrogen electrode.

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Table 1. Composition and Textual Results of the CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC Samples

Sample	BET surface areas (m ² /g)	Calculated surface area (m ² /g) ^a	Composition by ICP (mol%)		Composition by XPS (mol%)		Average particle size (nm) ^a	τ Scherrer (nm) ^b	Lattice parameter (Å) ^b
			Ce	Pr	Ce	Pr			
CeO ₂ NC	38	33	-	-	-	-	22	21	5.4
10%Pr-CeO ₂ NC	25	23	90.3	9.7	90.6	9.4	27	29	5.4

^aCalculated as an average of around 100 nanoparticles measured by TEM.

^bCalculated by Scherrer equation using XRD data.

Figure 1. HAADF-STEM images of (a) CeO_2 NC and (b) $10\%\text{Pr-CeO}_2$ NC; HREM images of (c), (e) CeO_2 NC and (d), (f) $10\%\text{Pr-CeO}_2$ NC samples in the $[001]$ and $[011]$ zone axis (DDPs shown as insets).

Figure 2. Edge length distributions of (a) CeO₂ NC and (b) 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC.

Figure 3. XRD patterns of CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC samples.

Figure 4. XPS spectra of (a) Pr 3d core level of as-synthesized 10%Pr-CeO₂ NCs and oxidized 10%Pr-CeO₂ NCs at 370 °C for 1 h in the catalytic chamber of XPS equipment, (b) Ce 3d core level of 10%Pr-CeO₂ and CeO₂ NCs.

Figure 5. (a) HAADF-STEM image of 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample. (b) A intensity profile along a line marked on the HAADF-STEM image in (a). (c) EELS spectra, in the Pr-Ce M_{4,5} energy loss region, representative of different locations of the spectrum-line experiment recorded along the line marked in (a): (I) average of 66 spectra at the bulk of the nanocube; (II) average of the 14 spectra corresponding to the first 3.5 nm from the surface; (III) average of the 4 spectra acquired at the first 1 nm layer from the surface.

Figure 6. H₂-TPR profiles of the nanocube samples. (a) The m/z: 18 signal corresponds to H₂O evolution. (b) The signal of m/z: 2 belongs to consumption of H₂.

Figure 7. OSC results for the CeO₂ NC and 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC samples.

Figure 8. (a) Scheme of the TMB oxidation; (b) UV-vis absorption spectra of TMB before and after mixing with 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC and the spectrum of a mixture of TMB and 10%Pr-CeO₂ with addition of sulfuric acid.

Figure 9. Changes of TMB absorbance at 652 nm during TMB oxidation catalyzed by different concentrations of nanoceria including 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC and CeO₂ NC.

Figure 10. Kinetic assays of TMB oxidation by 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC and CeO₂ NC while keeping the concentration of nanocubes constant. The solid line is the fit based on Michaelis-Menten kinetics equation and the inset is the corresponding lineweaver-Burk plot.

Figure 11. a) Electron transfer between TMB and CeO₂ NC (path 1) or 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC (path 1) during TMB oxidation. b) Valence band XPS signals corresponding to the 10%Pr-CeO₂ NC sample (green), 50% reduced pure ceria (red) and 100% reduced pure praseodymia (blue).